

A Study to Evaluate the Effectiveness of Self-Instructional Module on Knowledge Regarding Epilepsy among B.Ed. Students in Selected Colleges at Bijapur

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Abstract: Background: Epilepsy is one of the most common neurological diseases in the world. False knowledge and attitudes related to epilepsy both complicate the social lives of patients and adversely affect their academic development. The aim of this study was to investigate the Effectiveness of Self-Instructional Module on Knowledge Regarding Epilepsy among B.Ed. Students in Selected Colleges at Bijapur. **Objectives:** (1) To assess the knowledge of B.Ed. students regarding epilepsy before administration of self-instructional module. (2) To find the effectiveness of self-instructional module on epilepsy. (3) To find the association between the knowledge scores of B.Ed. students with selected socio demographic variables. **Methodology:** The research design used for this study is quasi experimental (one group pre-test) design. The independent variable is the self-instructional module and the dependent variable is knowledge of the B.Ed. students regarding epilepsy. **Results:** The results have revealed that in the pretest, majority of subjects 23(38.3%) had very poor knowledge, 33(55%) had poor knowledge, and 3(5%) had average knowledge and 1(1.66%) had good knowledge. It reveals that the mean percentage of knowledge scored was 26.66%. Reveals that the percentage of knowledge scores in the introduction of epilepsy was 42.8%, types of epilepsy was 25%, incidence of epilepsy was 20%, Causes of epilepsy 25%, phases of epilepsy 0%, Signs and symptoms of epilepsy was 0%, treatment of epilepsy 33.3%, complication of epilepsy 0%, prevention of epilepsy was 33.33%. **Interpretation and conclusion:** The findings of this study reveal that the Self-instructional module will increase the knowledge of the B.Ed. students on epilepsy and its prevention. Findings of the study shows that knowledge of the B.Ed. students percentage of introduction of epilepsy was 71.42%, types of epilepsy was 75%, incidence of epilepsy was 60%, Causes of epilepsy 75%, phases of epilepsy 100%, Signs and symptoms of epilepsy was 50%, treatment of epilepsy 100%, complication of epilepsy 100%, prevention of epilepsy was 100%. **Keywords:** Effectiveness, SIM, Knowledge, Epilepsy, B.Ed. students.

Introduction

Epilepsy is a chronic brain disorder characterized by recurrent derangement of the nervous system due to sudden excessive disorderly discharge of the aggregate group of neurons from cerebrum. The excessive discharges result in disturbances of sensation, convulsive movement, or psychic function with or without loss of consciousness [1]. Epilepsy affects all age groups but is more common in children. The reported prevalence of epilepsy in developing countries is 5 to 10 per 1000 people. Global prevalence is 2.8 to 19.5 per 1000 people [1]. Currently epilepsy affects 50 million people worldwide, of which 80% live in developing countries [2–4]. Many people in developing countries believe that epilepsy is contagious and spreads via urine, saliva, flatus and faeces excreted during a

convulsion. This belief has played a major role in people living with epilepsy being ostracized, stigmatized, and misunderstood [3]. Epilepsy continues to increase worldwide but, unfortunately, many B.Ed. students have inadequate knowledge and negative beliefs towards the disease. Hence early detection of problems and initiation of prompt management are the important responsibilities of B.Ed. students. Students should be adequately educated about epilepsy signs and their prevention.

Methodology

The research design used for this study is quasi experimental (one group pre-test) design. The independent variable is the self-instructional module and the dependent variable is knowledge of the B.Ed. students regarding epilepsy. This chapter describes the methodology followed to assess the knowledge and perception of epilepsy among B.Ed. students in selected colleges at Bijapur. The tool used for the study is self-administered knowledge Questionnaire to assess the knowledge of B.Ed. students regarding epilepsy. Content validity of the tool is given by experts and tool is found to be reliable and feasible. Self-instructional module is prepared to enhance the knowledge about epilepsy among B.Ed. students and is validated by the experts before administration. The main study was conducted for 4 weeks in the selected area of Bijapur. Pre-test was done to the B.Ed. students and assessed their knowledge.

Objectives of the study

- 1) To assess the knowledge of B.Ed. students regarding epilepsy before administration of self-instructional module.
- 2) To evaluate the effectiveness of self-instructional module on epilepsy.
- 3) To find out the association between the knowledge of B.Ed. students with selected socio-demographic variables.

Results

This chapter presents the analysis and interpretation of data collected from 60 B.Ed. students in the selected colleges at Bijapur regarding epilepsy by using a Self-administered knowledge questionnaire. Analysis is the process of organizing and synthesizing the data in such a way that research questions can be answered and hypotheses is tested. The purpose of the analysis is to reduce the data in an intelligible and interpretable form, so that the relation of research problem can be studied and tested. The purpose of the data analysis is to translate the information collected during the course of the study into interpretable form so that the research question could be answered. Data gathered were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The analysis of the data of the present study has been organized in relation to the objectives and hypotheses of the study.

Presentation of the data

The data is presented under the following sections:

Section I; Socio-demographic characteristics of the samples.

Section II: Assessment of knowledge of students regarding epilepsy.

Section III: Effectiveness of self-instructional module on epilepsy among students in the selected B.Ed. colleges at Bijapur, which is further categorized in to 4 parts:

Part 1: Comparison of knowledge level of students in the pretest and post-test.

Part 2: Area wise effectiveness of self-instructional module on knowledge regarding epilepsy among students in the selected B. Ed colleges at Bijapur.

Part 3: Testing Hypothesis.

Part 4: Association between knowledge score of students regarding epilepsy

Section I: Distribution of subject characteristics according to socio-demographic variables.

This section describes the characteristics of students in terms of age, gender, religion, type of family, family income, place of residence and source of information.

Table 1. Frequency and percentage distribution of subjects according to socio-demographic variables (n=60).

S. No.	Demographic Variables	No	%
1	Age (in years)		
	a) 20-25	33	55.0
	b) 26-30	21	35.0
	c) 31-35	6	10.0
	d) 36 and above	0	0.0
2	Gender		
	a) Male	25	41.7
	b) Female	35	58.3
3	Religion		
	a) Hindu	48	80.0
	b) Muslim	12	20.0
	c) Christian	0	0.0
	d) Others	0	0.0
4	Type of family		
	a) Nuclear family	39	65.0
	b) Joint family	14	23.3
	c) Extended family	7	11.7
5	Family income (In Rupees/month)		
	a) Less than 4000/-	6	10.0
	b) 4001/- 5000/-	16	26.7
	c) 5001/-10,000/-	26	43.3
	d) 10,000/- and Above	12	20.0
6	Place of residence		
	a) Rural	29	48.3
	b) Semi urban	18	30.0
	c) Urban	13	21.7
7	Source of information		
	a) Family and friends	8	13.3
	b) Books and magazines	31	51.7
	c) Internet	6	10.0
	d) Health care providers	15	25.0

- ✓ Maximum subjects i.e., 33 (41.7%) were in the age group of 20-25yrs, 21(35%) were in the age group of 26-30years, 6(10%) were in the age group of 31-35years and 0(0 %) of them were in the age group of 36 and above years.
- ✓ Maximum subjects i.e., 25(83.33%) were in male, and 35(58.3%) were in female.
- ✓ Maximum subjects i.e., 48(80%) were Hindu, 12(20%) were Muslim and 0(0%) were Christian and 0(0%) were others.
- ✓ Maximum subjects 39(65%) were nuclear family, 14(23.3%) were joint family, 7(11.7%) were extended family.
- ✓ Maximum subjects i.e., 6 (10 %) were in the monthly family income of <4000/-, were in the income of 4001-5000, 16(26.7%) were in the income of 5001-10,000/- and 26(43.3%) of them were in the income of above 10,000/-.
- ✓ Maximum subjects i.e., 29 (48.3 %) were as the place of residence at rural, 18(30 %) were as in the semi urban area, 13(21.7%) were as place of residence is urban.

- ✓ Maximum subjects i.e., 8(13.3%) student have information source of family and friends, 31(51.7 %) were source of books and magazines, 6(10 %) were in source of internet and 15(25 %) informational source from health care providers.

Section 1: Description of socio-demographic characteristics of the samples

Table 2. Frequency and percentage distribution of B.Ed. students according to Age.

Age in years	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
a) 20-25	33	55.0
b) 26-30	21	35.0
c) 31-35	6	10.0
d) 36 and above	0	0.0
Total	60	100

The above table 2, reveals that 33(55%) of the B.Ed. students were between the age group 20 to 25 years, 21(35%) of them were between the age group 26 to 30 years and 6 (10%) were between age group of 31 to 35years.

Table 3. Frequency and percentage distribution of B.Ed. students according to Gender.

Gender	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
a) Male	25	41.7
b) Female	35	58.3
Total	60	100

The above table-3 shows, that majority of the 25(41.7%) were Male and 35(58.3%) were Female respondents.

Table 4. Frequency and percentage distribution of B.Ed. students according to Religion.

Religion	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
a) Hindu	48	80.0
b) Muslim	12	20.0
c) Christian	0	0.0
d) Others	0	0.0
Total	60	100

The above table 4 shows, that majority of the B. Ed students 48(80%) were Hindu, 12 (20%) were Muslim respondents.

Table 5. Frequency and percentage distribution of B.Ed. students according to Type of Family.

Type of Family	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
a) Nuclear family	39	65.0
b) Joint family	14	23.3
c) Extended family	7	11.7
Total	60	100

The data represented in the table 5, depicts that, 39(65%) of the respondents were belongs to Nuclear family, 14(23.3%) of the respondents were belong joint family and 7 (11.7%) were belongs to extended family.

Table 6. Frequency and percentage distribution of B.Ed. students according to Income of Family.

Family income (In Rupees/month)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
a) Less than 4000/-	6	10.0
b) 4001/- 5000/-	16	26.7
c) 5001/-10,000/-	26	43.3
d) 10,000/- and Above	12	20.0
Total	60	100

The data represented in the table 6 depicts that, 6(10%) of respondents were belong to family income of less than 4000, 16(26.7%) of them were belongs to family income of 4001-5000, 26(43.3%) of respondents were between 5001-10000 and 12 (20%) of them were belong to more than 10000 income of family.

Table 7. Frequency and percentage distribution of B.Ed. students according to Place of residency

Place of residence	Frequency	Percentage (%)
a) Rural	29	48.3
b) Semi urban	18	30.0
c) Urban	13	21.7
Total	60	100

The data represented in the table 7 depicts that, 29(48.3%) of respondents were belong to Rural, 18(30%) of them were belongs to Semi urban, and 13 (21.7%) of them were belong to Urban areas.

Table 8. Frequency and percentage distribution of B.Ed. students according to Source of Information.

Source of information	Frequency	Percentage (%)
a) Family and friends	8	13.3
b) Books and magazines	31	51.7
c) Internet	6	10.0
d) Health care providers	15	25.0
Total	60	100

The data represented in the table 8 depicts that, 8(13.3%) of respondents were getting information from family and friends, 31(51.7%) of them were getting information from books and magazines, 6(10%) of respondents were getting information from internet and 15 (25%) of them were getting information from Health care providers.

Section 2: Assessment of knowledge of the students regarding epilepsy.

Table 9. Pretest knowledge regarding epilepsy among B.Ed. students (n=60)

Level of knowledge	Score	No of Respondents	
		No	%
Inadequate	<50%	33	55.0
Moderate	50-75%	24	40.0
Adequate	>75%	3	5.0
Total		60	100

The data represented in the table 9 represents pretest knowledge of B.Ed. students regarding Epilepsy and also reveals that the level of knowledge of B Ed students before using self-instructional module.

In that 33(55%) of respondents were have inadequate knowledge, 24(40%) of them have moderate knowledge and 3(5%) of respondents have adequate knowledge.

Table 10. Post-test knowledge regarding epilepsy among B.Ed. students (n=60)

Level of knowledge	Score	No of Respondents	
		No	%
Inadequate	<50%	0	0.0
Moderate	50-75%	39	65.0
Adequate	>75%	21	35.0
Total		60	100

The data represented in the table 10 represents post-test knowledge of B.Ed. students regarding Epilepsy after using self- instructional module. In that 0(0%) of respondents were have inadequate knowledge, 39(65%) of them have moderate knowledge and 21(35%) of respondents have adequate knowledge.

Section III: Assessment of effectiveness of self-instructional module on epilepsy among students in the selected B.Ed. colleges at Bijapur. This is further categorized in to 4 parts:

Part 1: Comparison of knowledge level of students in the pretest and post test

Table 11. Comparison of pre and post knowledge regarding epilepsy among B.Ed. students (n=60)

Level of knowledge	Score	Pre test		Post test	
		No	%	No	%
Inadequate	<50%	33	55.0	0	0.0
Moderate	50-75%	24	40.0	39	65.0
Adequate	>75%	3	5.0	21	35.0
Total		60	100	60	100

Part 2: Area wise effectiveness of Self-instructional module on knowledge

Table 12. Mean, SD and mean% of knowledge regarding epilepsy among B.Ed. students (n=60)

Knowledge	Max statement	Max Score	Mean	SD	Mean %
Pre test	30	30	16.3	3.5	54.3
Post test	30	30	26.5	2.7	88.3

Table 13. Evaluate the Effectiveness of Self- Instructional Module on Knowledge Regarding Epilepsy among B.Ed. students

Knowledge	Mean	SD	Mean %	t -value
Pre test	16.3	3.5	54.3	31.6**
Post test	26.5	2.7	88.3	
Enhancement	10.2	2.5	34	
** Significant at P<0.01, (df 59, t value 2)				

Table 13 states that the effectiveness of self -instructional module in terms of gaining knowledge scores in post- test. According to this B.Ed. students pre-test knowledge regarding Epilepsy was 16.3 and post-test knowledge regarding Epilepsy was 26.5, which is significant, so there is enough evidence that self- instructional module is effective in enhancing the knowledge of the B.Ed. students regarding Epilepsy.

Part 3: Testing Hypothesis

To evaluate the effectiveness of self-instructional module, research hypothesis is formulated.

H₁: There will be significant difference between the pre-test knowledge and post-test knowledge scores of students regarding epilepsy.

Part4: Association between knowledge score of staff nurses regarding pneumonia and its prevention.

Table 14. To determine the association between demographic variables and level of knowledge of B.Ed. students.

S. No.	Socio Demographic Variables	No	%	No of Respondents				Chi-square
				≤ Median (27)	> Median (33)			
1	Age in years							
	a) 20-25	33	55.0	19	57.6	14	42.4	4.72
	b) 26-30	21	35.0	6	28.6	15	71.4	df 2
	c) 31-35	6	10.0	2	33.3	4	66.7	N.S
	d) 36 and above	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	
2	Gender							
	a) Male	25	41.7	15	60.0	10	40.0	3.9
	b) Female	35	58.3	12	34.3	23	65.7	df 1 S
3	Religion							
	a) Hindu	48	80.0	20	41.7	28	58.3	0.18
	b) Muslim	12	20.0	7	58.3	5	41.7	df 1
	c) Christian	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	N.S
	d) Others	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	
4	Type of family							
	a) Nuclear family	39	65.0	19	48.7	20	51.3	1
	b) Joint family	14	23.3	6	42.9	8	57.1	df 2
	c) Extended family	7	11.7	2	28.6	5	71.4	N.S
5	Family income (In Rupees/month)							
	a) Less than 4000/-	6	10.0	3	50.0	3	50.0	12.9
	b) 4001/- 5000/-	16	26.7	9	56.3	7	43.8	df 3
	c) 5001/-10,000/-	26	43.3	15	57.7	11	42.3	S
	d) 10,000/- and Above	12	20.0	0	0.0	12	100.0	
6	Place of residence							
	a) Rural	29	48.3	17	58.6	12	41.4	4.9
	b) Semi urban	18	30.0	7	38.9	11	61.1	df 2
	c) Urban	13	21.7	3	23.1	10	76.9	N.S
7	Source of information							
	a) Family and friends	8	13.3	5	62.5	3	37.5	9.5
	b) Books and magazines	31	51.7	18	58.1	13	41.9	df 3
	c) Internet	6	10.0	2	33.3	4	66.7	S
	d) Health care providers	15	25.0	2	13.3	13	86.7	
N.S-Not Significant; S-Significant at p<0.05 level								

Chi square test was used to find the association between the socio- demographic variables and knowledge of subjects regarding epilepsy. No significant association was found between the knowledge of epilepsy and their socio-demographic variables: Age, religion, type of family and place of residence, significant association was found between the knowledge of epilepsy and their socio-demographic variables: gender, family income, sources of information.

Summary

This chapter dealt with the analysis and interpretation of the findings of the study. The data gathered were summarized in the master sheet and both descriptive and inferential statistics were used for analysis. In overall findings reveals that the post-test knowledge scores was more than (21.6±6.41) when compared to pre- test knowledge score (7.6±7.09). Hence it indicates that the SIM was effective in enhancing the knowledge of students.

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts of interest.

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